

1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions. Part-XV : Systematic spectroscopic investigations of C-aryl-N-methylnitrones¹

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Abstract : Several C-aryl-N-methylnitrones have been synthesised during the course of our work on 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions. Detailed systematic spectroscopic investigations of all these nitrones have been undertaken. These are reported along with some generalisations made regarding their spectroscopic properties.

Keywords : C-Aryl-N-methylnitrones, UV, IR, NMR, MS.

Introduction

Isoxazoles can be considered as masked forms of various 1,3-difunctionalised compounds namely 1,3-dicarbonyl, enaminketone, γ -amino alcohol, α,β -unsaturated oxime, β -hydroxy nitrile or β -hydroxyketone compounds^{2,3}. One of the major routes to the isoxazole ring system is the 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions of alkenes and alkynes with nitrones²⁻⁴. Nitrones can be synthesised by the conventional technique of heating the reactants (aldehydes/ketones and N-substituted hydroxylamines) for a period of time in an appropriate solvent⁵. Fairly lengthy procedures and occurrence of some degree of decomposition for the preparation of several nitrones, led us to invoke the assistance of an improved procedure of nitrone synthesis utilising the microwave irradiation technique^{6,7}.

In our previous studies^{6,7}, we reported the successfully utilised microwave irradiation procedure for synthesising a series of aldonitrones from aromatic aldehydes. In the procedure developed from our laboratory to synthesise the C-aryl-N-methylnitrones, a mixture of the appropriate aromatic aldehyde with a small excess (1 : 1.3–1.4 molar ratio) of N-methylhydroxylamine hydrochloride in anhydrous dichloromethane and excess sodium hydrogen carbonate was subjected to microwave irradiation for a period usually ranging from 2–6 min. The yields were usually above 90%. This procedure was reported in an earlier communication⁶. We found that though there are some scattered reports of spectroscopic

properties of nitrones in general, systematic studies had not been undertaken. In a previous communication of this series, we have reported the synthesis of C,N-diarylnitrones and a systematic spectroscopical investigation of these nitrones⁷. In the present communication, we report our detailed and systematic spectroscopic investigations of eleven C-aryl-N-methylnitrones, and some generalisations regarding their spectroscopic properties.

Spectroscopic analyses of the C-aryl-N-methylnitrones :

Ultraviolet spectra : A few papers have earlier reported the UV absorption characteristics of nitrones⁸⁻¹². These deal with several aspects such as the influence of steric effects⁹ and of solvent effects¹⁰ upon the UV spectra of nitrones. In case of nitrones, a characteristic strong $\pi-\pi^*$ band appears in the region 280–370 nm in addition to one or two relatively low intensity bands in the region 200–260 nm. The molecular extinction coefficient ranges to about 20000 in the former. Kubota, Yamakawa and Mori have studied the electronic spectra of various nitrones in various solvents like CCl₄, *n*-heptane, ethanol, methanol and water^{8(b)}. They observed that steric hindrance leads to the decrease in the intensity of the characteristic strong $\pi-\pi^*$ band of nitrones. Blue shifts of the absorption bands of all nitrones are caused by the increasing polarity of those solvents which can form hydrogen bonds like N \rightarrow O \cdots H-O⁻ (solvents); however, log ϵ_{\max} values were reported to be virtually unaltered. UV spectra of some selected C-aryl-N-methylnitrones were recorded

Scheme 1

using methanol as the solvent. The λ_{max} values were lowered by 7–9 nm in ethanol compared to that in cyclohexane with unaltered $\log \epsilon_{\text{max}}$ values. In case of *C*-aryl-*N*-methylnitrones, we observed that the nitrone with unsubstituted *C*-phenyl group ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 299$ nm in cyclohexane and 292 nm in case of ethanol) and its 4-chloro derivative ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 302$ nm in methanol, $\log \epsilon_{\text{max}} : 4.00$), exhibit nearly equal λ_{max} values. Owing to the electron-withdrawing nature of the nitro group, the λ_{max} for π - π^* transition gets enhanced to 335 nm (in methanol, $\log \epsilon_{\text{max}} : 3.92$) in case of *C*-(4-nitrophenyl)-*N*-methylnitrones.

Infrared spectra : The IR spectra of all the nitrones (1–11) were recorded in KBr pellets using a Perkin-Elmer RX-9 FT-IR spectrophotometer. Nitrones exhibit two characteristic bands, corresponding to the N–O and C=N⁺< bond-stretching vibrations. In these aldonitrones (1–11), the N–O band appears in the range 1159–1185 cm^{-1} . The C=N⁺< stretching vibration appears at 1577–1602 cm^{-1} . This band appears at 1599 cm^{-1} in the *C*-phenyl compound (1). It shifts to a twin band at 1591 and 1577 cm^{-1} in the *C*-(4-nitrophenyl)nitron (2) and to 1603 cm^{-1} in the *C*-(4-methoxyphenyl)nitron (8) respectively, the (–R effect) 4-nitro group and the (+R effect) 4-methoxy group shifting this band in opposite directions. Additional olefinic conjugation to the phenyl in (11) shifts this band to a lower frequency – 1565 cm^{-1} . These compare with the stretching vibrations for *C*-aryl-*N*-phenyl-nitrones – 1175–1192 cm^{-1} (for the N–O stretching) and 1544–1600 cm^{-1} (for the C=N⁺< stretching). The comparative band positions for *C,N*-diphenylnitron and *C*-phenyl-*N*-methylnitrones are 1185, 1545 cm^{-1} and 1163, 1598 cm^{-1} respectively. In addition to the characteristic absorptions of the nitrone functionality, absorption bands for the aromatic moieties, and for the C–Cl, C–Br, C–OCH₃ and nitro groups (wherever appropriate) were observed.

¹H NMR spectra : The 300 MHz ¹H NMR spectra show certain common characteristic features. The nitrone proton –C–H=N(Me)⁺–O[–], appears downfield at δ 7.36 as a singlet in *C*-phenyl-*N*-methylnitron. The position of the signal is not substantially affected by change of substituent in most of these nitrones. However, the presence of a *p*- or *m*-nitro group deshields this slightly by ~0.2 ppm. The chemical shift of this proton appears ~0.6 ppm upfield compared to the *C*-aryl-*N*-phenylnitrones. The *N*-methyl group in *C*-phenyl-*N*-methylnitron (1) appears at a comparatively low field value of δ 3.87, due to the electron-withdrawing nitrone functionality. Essentially, aryl substituent effects are negligible, though a *p*- or *m*-nitro substituent deshields the signal by 0.1 ppm, the 4-methoxy substituent shields it by 0.15 ppm. The *ortho*-protons of the aryl ring are deshielded by the electron-withdrawing nitrone functionality. Two conformations are possible for these nitrones, viz. (I) and (II). The proton nearer to oxygen is more deshielded due to deshielding effect of the oxygen bearing a total negative charge. However, due to a low conformational barrier, H_a and H_b interchange their positions very rapidly; thus the ¹H NMR spectrum shows a time-averaged chemical shift for this proton. This is true for the *C*-phenyl and *para*- and *meta*-substituted phenyl rings, where equal (or nearly equal for the *meta*-substituted rings) proportions of both conformers are present at equilibrium.

However, if an *ortho*-substituent, such as *ortho*-methoxyl group is present, it imposes a larger conformational barrier between the alternative conformations (III) and (IV) and also affects the conformational equilibrium in favour of the less hindered conformation (III). As a result, this proton (H-6) appears at the downfield position of δ 9.22.

A rough estimate about the approximate chemical shifts of H_a and H_b in *C*-phenyl-*N*-methylnitronium (1) can be made in the following way. The chemical shift of H_a in (1/I) can be calculated as $\sim \delta$ 9.3 ppm, allowing for a small shielding factor of $\sim \delta$ 0.1 ppm for the *meta*-substituted methoxy group in (9). Since the time-averaged value for the *ortho*-protons is δ 8.2 ppm in (1/I), the chemical shift for H_b is calculated to be $\sim \delta$ 7.1 ppm.

¹³C NMR spectra : The 75.5 MHz ¹³C NMR of some selected *C*-aryl-*N*-methylnitroniums, viz. (2), (4), (5), (7),

(8) were recorded. The nitronium CH signal appeared in the low-field region δ 132.9–134.7 ppm, while the *N*-methyl group appeared in the region δ 54.2–55.1 ppm. The ¹³C NMR assignments were confirmed on the basis of multiplicities determined on the basis of DEPT spectra, substituent chemical shifts (SCS) and intercomparisons among the ¹³C NMR spectra of these compounds.

Mass spectral fragmentation of C-aryl-N-methyl-nitroniums :

Mass spectra : The mass spectral fragmentation pattern of a typical nitronium, *C*-(4-chlorophenyl)-*N*-methyl-nitronium (4) is shown in Scheme 2. The loss of an oxygen atom is typical of a nitronium. Cyclisation of the nitronium functionality to an oxaziridine, subsequent rearrangement to an amide and fragmentation generates the chlorobenzoyl cation. The fragments containing chlorine showed the expected P : P+2 = 3 : 1 pattern, and helped to elucidate the fragmentation pattern

Experimental

UV Spectra of the nitroniums were recorded in dry methanol using a Shimadzu UV-3101 PC spectrophotometer. The IR spectra of all the nitroniums (1-11) were recorded in KBr pellets using a Perkin-Elmer RX-9 FT-IR spectro-

Scheme 2. Mass spectral fragmentation of (4).

photometer with a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} . NMR spectra of the samples were analysed in CDCl_3 solution using Bruker AM-300L and Bruker AV-300 NMR spectrometers.

C-Phenyl-N-methylnitrone (1) :

White crystals from ethanol, m.p. 85° , IR : $\nu = 1599$ (s, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1163 (s, N-O), 757, 693 (m, mono-substituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.36 (1H, s, $-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 3.87 (3H, s, $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 8.20 (2H, dd, J 7.4, 3.0, Ar, H-2,6), 7.39-7.41 (3H, m, Ar, H-3,4,5) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 75.5 MHz) : 135.9 ($-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 54.1 (N- CH_3), 130.3 (Ar, C-2,6), 128.3 (Ar, C-1,3,4,5).

C-(4-Nitrophenyl)-N-methylnitrone (2) :

Yellow crystals from ethanol, m.p. 203° , UV (methanol) : λ_{max} (nm) = 335 [log ϵ_{max} : 3.92] IR : $\nu = 1577$, 1591 (m, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1166 (s, N-O), 1510, 1336 (s, Ar- NO_2), 865 (m, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.54 (1H, s, $-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 3.96 (3H, s, $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 8.38 (2H, d, J 7.2, Ar, H-2,6), 8.26 (2H, d, J 7.2, Ar, H-3,5) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 75.5 MHz) : 132.9 ($-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 55.1 (N- CH_3), 136.1 (Ar, C-1), 128.7 (Ar, C-2,6), 123.8 (Ar, C-3,5), 148.0 (Ar, C-4).

C-(3-Nitrophenyl)-N-methylnitrone (3) :

Yellow crystals from ethanol, m.p. 180° , IR : $\nu = 1584$ (m, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1172 (s, N-O), 1521, 1350 (s, Ar- NO_2), 825, 729 (m, 1,3-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.54 (1H, s, $-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 3.95 (3H, s, $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 9.00 (1H, s, Ar, H-2), 8.23 (1H, d, J 7.8, Ar, H-6), 7.60 (2H, t, J 7.8, Ar, H-5), 8.62 (1H, br, d, J 7.8, Ar, H-4) ppm.

C-(4-Chlorophenyl)-N-methylnitrone (4) :

White crystals from ethanol, m.p. 132° , UV (methanol) : λ_{max} (nm) = 302 [log ϵ_{max} : 4.00] IR : $\nu = 1592$ (m, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1184 (s, N-O), 1087 (s, Ar-Cl), 855 (m, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.36 (1H, s, $-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 3.87 (3H, s, $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 8.17 (2H, d, J 8.7, B, H-2,6), 7.38 (2H, d, J 8.7, B, H-3,5) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 75.5 MHz) : 133.5 ($-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 54.2 (N- CH_3), 128.9 (Ar, C-1), 129.3 (Ar, C-2,6), 128.4 (Ar, C-3,5), 135.4 (Ar, C-4).

C-(3-Chlorophenyl)-N-methylnitrone (5) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 137° , IR : $\nu = 1588$ (s, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1169 (s, N-O), 1093 (m, Ar-Cl), 896, 797 (m, 1,3-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR

(CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.33 (1H, s, $-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 3.88 (3H, s, $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 8.33 (1H, s, Ar, H-2), 7.35-7.36 (2H, m, Ar, H-4,5), 7.80 (1H, d, J 7.1, Ar, H-6) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 75.5 MHz) : 133.9 ($-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 54.6 (N- CH_3), 132.8 (Ar, C-1), 130.4 (Ar, C-2), 134.4 (Ar, C-3), 128.0 (Ar, C-5), 129.7 (Ar, C-4), 126.5 (Ar, C-6).

C-(4-Bromophenyl)-N-methylnitrone (6) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 140° , IR : $\nu = 1587$ (s, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1167 (m, N-O), 446 (m, Ar-Br), 854 (m, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.27 (1H, s, $-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 3.80 (3H, s, $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 8.00 (2H, d, J 8.6, Ar, H-2,6), 7.47 (2H, d, J 8.6, Ar, H-3,5) ppm.

C-(3-Bromophenyl)-N-methylnitrone (7) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 145° , IR : $\nu = 1587$ (s, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1172 (s, N-O), 947 (m, Ar-Br), 786, 683 (s, 1,3-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.33 (1H, s, $-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 3.89 (3H, s, $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 8.46 (1H, s, B, H-2), 8.06 (1H, d, J 7.8, Ar, H-6), 7.28 (1H, t, J 7.6, Ar, H-5), 7.53 (1H, d, J 7.4, Ar, H-4) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 75.5 MHz) : 133.7 ($-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 54.6 (N- CH_3), 132.4 (Ar, C-1), 133.3 (Ar, C-2), 122.6 (Ar, C-3), 129.9 (Ar, C-4), 126.8 (Ar, C-5), 130.8 (Ar, C-6).

C-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-N-methylnitrone (8) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 142° , IR : $\nu = 1603$ (m, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1160 (s, N-O), 1259 (s), 1027 (m, C-O-C), 847 (s, 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.21 (1H, s, $-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 3.72 (3H, s, $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 3.74 (3H, s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 8.11 (2H, d, J 8.9, Ar, H-2,6), 6.82 (2H, d, J 8.9, Ar, H-3,5) ppm; ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 75.5 MHz) : 134.7 ($-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 54.9 (N- CH_3), 53.4 (OCH_3), 123.2 (Ar, C-1), 130.0 (Ar, C-2,6), 113.5 (Ar, C-3,5), 160.7 (Ar, C-4).

C-(2-Methoxyphenyl)-N-methylnitrone (9) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 150° , IR : $\nu = 1591$ (s, $>\text{C}=\text{N}^+<$), 1168 (s, N-O), 1244 (s), 1023 (m, C-O-C), 750 (m) cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , δ , 300 MHz) : 7.82 (1H, s, $-\text{HC}=\text{N}^+<$), 3.82 (3H, s, $>\text{N}-\text{CH}_3$), 3.84 (3H, s, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 9.22 (1H, d, J 7.9, Ar, H-6), 6.88 (1H, d, J 8.4, Ar, H-3), 7.00 (1H, br, t, $J \sim 7.7$, Ar, H-5), 7.36 (1H, br, t, J 7.5, Ar, H-4) ppm.

C-(Furfuryl)-N-methylnitrone (10) :

White crystals from ethanol, m.p. 83° , UV (methanol) : λ_{max} (nm) = 302.50 [log ϵ_{max} = 4.14] IR : $\nu =$

1656 (s, >C=C<), 1148 (s, N-O), 1599 (m, >C=N⁺<), 1231 (s, C-O), 757 (s), 819 (s), 939 (s) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ, 300 MHz) : 7.47 (1H, s, -HC=N⁺<), 3.75 (3H, s, >N-CH₃), 7.41 (1H, d, *J* 1.6, Ar, H-3), 6.48 (1H, dd, *J* 1.6, 3.5, Ar, H-4), 7.68 (1H, d, *J* 3.5, Ar, H-5) ppm; ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, δ, 75.5 MHz) : 126.2 (-HC=N⁺<), 52.7 (N-CH₃), 146.7 (Ar, C-2), 115.2 (Ar, C-3), 112.2 (Ar, C-4), 143.6 (Ar, C-5).

C-(Cinnamoyl)-*N*-methylnitrone (11) :

Crystals from ethanol, m.p. 145°, IR : ν = 1565 (m, >C=N⁺<), 1176 (m, N-O), 1660, 1607 (m, >C=C<), 753, 695 (m, mono-substituted benzene ring) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, δ, 300 MHz) : 7.28 (1H, d, *J* 9.6, -HC=N⁺<), 3.71 (3H, s, >N-CH₃), 6.93 (1H, d, *J* 15.8, H-β), 7.43 (1H, dd, *J* 15.8, 9.6, H-α), 7.51 (2H, dd, *J* 7.8, 2.6, Ar, H-2,6), 7.25-7.40 (2H, m, Ar, H-3,5), 7.22 (1H, t, *J* 8.1, Ar, H-4).

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